

A Supervised Learning Model for Predicting the Impact of COVID-19 on Student Mental in Higher Education

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords</p> <p>Applied Informatics, Artificial Intelligence, COVID-19, Disruptive Technology, Educational Data Mining</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5557777</p>	<p><i>Predicting the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) situation on student mental in higher education was consistent with the belief that prevention is better than cure. Therefore, the main objective of this research was to study the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic situation on the risks of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education. The specific objectives consisted of (1) to investigate the relationship between the risks, (2) to formulate a reasonable predictive model with machine learning, and (3) to evaluate a predictive model. The samples were obtained from students at the University of Phayao who were enrolled in the academic year 2020. The data were from 925 students affiliated with 11 affiliations. Research tools include basic statistical tools such as average, standard deviation, proportion, percentage, and machine learning tools such as decision tree classification, cross-validation methods, confusion matrix performance, accuracy, precision, and recall. The results showed that the impact of COVID-19 pandemic scenario on the students was substantial. It leads to risks of depression, anxiety, and stress of students. The researcher was able to develop a model of high accuracy. It showed that the depression risk analysis model has high performance with an accuracy of 72.76%, the anxiety risk analysis model has high performance with an accuracy of 78.37%, and the stress risk analysis model has also high performance with an accuracy of 91.78%.</i></p>

Introduction

The impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) creates catastrophic events on humanity and massive violence. It damages the economy, society, and education (Ch & Habibulla, 2021; Chang et al., 2021; Dechsupa et al., 2020; Goodwin et al., 2021; Katewongsa et al., 2021; Levitskyi et al., 2021; Pongutta et al., 2021; Wichaidit et al., 2021). While Thailand's education has been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic in many dimensions. Moreover, learner quality and educational processes are an important part of academic achievement. It was also greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Modifications and the necessity of relying on technology to solve problems in the COVID-19 create disturbance in society as well. The focus is on the replacement of the technology known as disruptive technology (Gercek et al., 2016; Grant et al., 2013; P. Nuankaew et al., 2021; W. Nuankaew & Nuankaew, 2021; Vorbach et al., 2019). It is to bring technology to change the normal process. An important example in the education system is the application of online teaching and learning methods to solve the problem of social distance. In order to implement the technology, investment is required. It consists of the need to have a device that can learn through online learning systems, or the presence of a high-speed Internet network to transmit and communicate with each other unstable. From a variety of issues that affect the mental health of learners and related parties. The important thing is to be prepared for unexpected changes.

Therefore, the purpose of this research is comprised of three targets: (1) to investigate the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education, (2) to formulate a reasonable predictive model of the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education with machine learning, and (3) to evaluate a predictive model of the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education. While the scope of this research is limited to study in university students. The research population is students in the University of Phayao. It consists of eleven affiliations: School of Agriculture and Natural Resources, School of Business and Communication Arts, School of Education, School of Engineering, School of Information and Communication Technology, School of Law,

School of Liberal Arts, School of Medical Sciences, School of Medicine, School of Political and Social Science, and School of Science. The scope of data collection is during the first semester, and the second semester of the academic year 2020.

In addition, the paper outline consists of six main sections: the first of which is to draw attention to the problems of the research, which was presented in the introduction section. The second section is to visualize common understanding from literature reviews and related research. The third section describes the scientific research process. The fourth section is the research report and the findings from the research process for which it was designed. The fifth section is a discussion of research findings to improve research. The last section is the conclusion that aims to summarize the research and present future research guidelines. Finally, the review of the problems and understanding of the COVID-19 pandemic situation reflects the importance and necessity of this research.

Related Works

Data mining is associated with the search for new knowledge in the vast amount of data and information (Meyers, 2002). Most of these findings are obtained in the pattern of rules that are not known to the user before and could be of significant benefit in the future. An importance feature to be implemented in data mining is that it provides user interfaces at all levels and allows end users to identify problems leading to user-friendly results.

In psychology and medicine, data mining is analyzed using various machine learning techniques. For example: data mining algorithms and techniques in mental health (Alonso et al., 2018), it compiles research that applies data mining and machine learning tools to mental health. It has been found that data mining techniques and algorithms are applied to dementia. It uses different machine learning tools, including decision tree techniques usage up to 62.50 percent, artificial neural networks techniques usage 62.50 percent, logistic regression techniques usage 37.50 percent, naïve bayes techniques usage 12.50 percent, and so on. Meanwhile (Alonso et al., 2018) has deployed the data mining techniques and algorithms in depression. It found that the most popular technique was Support Vector Machine (SVM), with 45.45 percent of tool implementations. The second technique is naïve bayes with 36.36 percent. The third technique has three techniques: decision tree, random forest, and logistic regression as 27.27 percent. Another important research example is the use of data mining for healthcare ("Data Mining in Healthcare – A Review," 2015). It presents the various methods used in research such as anomaly detection, clustering, classification, discriminant analysis, decision tree, swan intelligence, k-nearest neighbor, logistic regression, Bayesian classifier, and support vector machine (SVM). These are tools and research examples related to data mining analysis for health management. Based on the relevant research samples, the researcher is confident that it can lead to research in this work.

Research Methodology

The research process believes in science. Therefore, research is carried out according to the principle of developing knowledge from data mining known as CRISP-DM: Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (Chapman et al., 2000; Huber et al., 2019; Jair et al., 2017; Shafique & Qaiser, 2014). The key steps of the CRISP-DM principle consist of six scientific steps: Business Understanding, Data Understanding, Data Preparation, Modeling, Evaluation, and Deployment as detailed in this section.

Business Understanding

Business Understanding (BU) phase is an important goal of the research process. It is responsible for formulating research questions and creating awareness among research readers (Chapman et al., 2000; Wirth & Hipp, 2000). It is clear that this research aims to address the national issue of the impact of the coronavirus 2019 pandemic.

The focus of the research reflects the impact on students in higher education affected by the devastating impact of the coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. The process of understanding the impact of coronavirus disease 2019 on students in higher education was developed through a questionnaire which the researcher designed in two dimensions: perceived impact on COVID-19 and impact on the vulnerability to depression, anxiety, and stress among students in higher education as discussing the process of data understanding.

Data Understanding

The phase of the Data Understanding (DU) is to pass on the understanding of the problem in preparation for forwarding the data collection method (Chapman et al., 2000; Shafique & Qaiser, 2014; Wirth & Hipp, 2000). The importance of data understanding is extracting the essence of the problem and creating a process for collecting information. This research has extracted the problems and created a questionnaire and selected the original

questionnaire which is already effective. It is known as Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21)(Antony et al., 1998; Norton, 2007; Oei et al., 2013).

Consequently, there are three main sections of this research: the first section collected general information of the respondents, the second section was compiled from an attitude questionnaire on the impact of the COVID-19 situation as detailed in Table 1, and the third part gathered the risk of respondents to analyze the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress among students at the University of Phayao.

The impact level and the rating scale are divided into two parts as follows: The first part has five levels of impact from the COVID pandemic scenario: level 0 is no impact, level 1 has a small impact, level 2 has moderate impact, level 3 has a large impact, and Level 4 has the most severe impact. While the second scale is classified into four scales as follows: level 0 did not occur to the respondents at all, level 1 has occurred to the respondents at some level or at some time, level 2 has occurred to the respondents at a considerable degree or a good part of time, and level 3 has occurred to the respondents at very much or most of the time.

The interpretation or explanation of the results was also classified into two parts, with the first classified by the statistical values as shown in the interpretation in Table 1. While the depression, anxiety and stress results were interpreted in Table 4.

Table 1. Questions Regarding the Pandemic Scenario of Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19)

Perspective	The level of impact caused by COVID-19				
	0	1	2	3	4
Learning Management Dimensions					
1. Problems of opening/closing the semester					
2. Online learning methods					
3. Equipment in online learning					
4. How to access the online learning system					
5. Impact on learning					
Economic, Social, and Daily Life Dimensions					
6. Impact of university travel					
7. Services and welfare in the university					
8. Impact of university activities					
9. University lifestyle					
10. Impact of the government measures					
Interpersonal Dimension					
11. Impact of relationships between friends					
12. Impact of family relationships					

Table 1 presents questions to study the perceptions and impacts that learner receive from the COVID-19 pandemic situation. It consists of three issues and twelve questions. Where the degree of impact given the scope of the questionnaire consists of four levels, as described above. In addition, the data obtained from the respondents were interpreted as shown in the interpretation criteria in Table 3.

Table 2. DASS-21 Questionnaire (Antony et al., 1998)

Questions	Rating Scale			
	0	1	2	3
1 (s) I found it hard to wind down				
2 (a) I was aware of dryness of my mouth				
3 (d) I could not seem to experience any positive feeling at all				
4 (a) I experienced breathing difficulty				
5 (d) I found it difficult to work up the initiative to do things				
6 (s) I tended to over-react to situations				
7 (a) I experienced trembling				
8 (s) I felt that I was using a lot of nervous energy				
9 (a) I was worried about situations in which I might panic and make a fool of myself				
10 (d) I felt that I had nothing to look forward to				
11 (s) I found myself getting agitated				
12 (s) I found it difficult to relax				
13 (d) I felt down hearted and blue				
14 (s) I was intolerant of anything that kept me from getting on with what I was doing				
15 (a) I felt I was close to panic				
16 (d) I was unable to become enthusiastic about anything				
17 (d) I felt I was not worth much as a person				
18 (s) I felt that I was rather touchy				
19 (a) I was aware of the action of my heart in the absence of physical exertion				

Questions	Rating Scale			
	0	1	2	3
20 (a) I felt scared without any good reason				
21 (d) I felt that life was meaningless				

Table 2 details questions based on the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS-21) principle. It consists of 21 questions which are grouped into three categories: depression risk, anxiety risk, and stress risk. The data obtained from the respondents were interpreted and calculated as shown in the interpretation criteria in Table 4.

Table 3. Interpretation COVID-19 Impact

Average Score	Interpretation
0.00 - 0.79	No Impact
0.80 - 1.59	Small Impact
1.60 - 2.39	Moderate Impact
2.40 - 3.19	Large Impact
3.20 - 4.00	Most Severe Impact

Table 3 presents the interpretation criteria of results from the analysis of data, perceptions, and attitudes of students in higher education.

Table 4. Scores on the DASS-21 and Labels

	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
Normal	0 - 9	0 - 7	0 - 14
Mild	10 - 13	8 - 9	15 - 18
Moderate	14 - 20	10 - 14	19 - 25
Severe	21 - 27	15 - 19	26 - 33
Extremely Severe	28+	20+	34+

Table 4 presents the interpretive criteria of results from the data analysis of the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education.

Data Preparation

Data Preparation (DP) phase is the phase that takes the most amount of time in the data mining process. It plays an important role in preparing the collected data for the model development process. In addition, the data preparation phase is also a switch during the model development process (modeling phase), which occasionally required multiple data provisioning (Wirth & Hipp, 2000).

For this research, the preparation of the data was divided into two main sections: the first section was the preparation to analyze the data for quantitative research. The tool used in this section is to describe the overall attitude of the respondents. It consists of mean, standard deviation, proportion, and percentage. The researcher analyzed the results in this section and presented them in the reporting section. While the second section was to analyze the relationship between perception and attitudes towards the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress. At this stage, the researcher designed a reduction process for assessing the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress using data mining and machine learning techniques. The reduction was to use a decision tree classification technique to analyze attitudes to the COVID-19 situation along with the history of depression risk, anxiety, and stress. The process of making decision trees is aimed at modeling relationships between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education with machine learning. The modeling process was expanded and explained in the stage of modeling.

Modeling

Modeling (M) phase is an important process for systematically using prepared data to create a model for solving research or business problems (Wirth & Hipp, 2000).

The model developed in this process focused on an objective analysis to establish a reasonable predictive model of the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education with machine learning. The

relationship analysis tool and technique for this purpose is the decision tree classification technique. The decision trees were implemented for mapping attitudes towards the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic situation in various risk scenarios, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Applying Machine Learning and Data Mining to Modeling

Figure 1 shows the applying of machine learning and data mining for model development to map the impact of COVID-19 on various risk situations. It consists of three key parts, the first part being a collection of factors and impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. The second part was to take impact data analyzed with machine learning and data mining to develop the model as mentioned in Figure 2. Finally, the third part is to present the vulnerability of new datasets obtained in the future. This will occur when the developed and selected model is positioned into an application that will be developed in future research.

Fig. 2. Applying Machine Learning and Data Mining to Modeling

Figure 2 describes the modeling process and the model testing process to select an efficient and reasonable model. It consists of four key steps: Step 1 is the normal data analysis as defined; Step 2 is the selection of relevant data to develop the decision tree model, Step 3 is cross-validation test for evaluation, and Step 4 is to determine the model's efficiency.

Evaluation

Evaluation (E) phase is part of determining the suitability of the prototype model that has been developed (Chapman et al., 2000). There are different types of model consideration processes. It depends on the suitability of the model implementation.

The process of evaluating the models in this research is divided into three combinations. The first part is cross-validation testing. Its principle is to divide the data into numbered parts (k) that the researcher determines. After that, some data were used for model development (training data) and the rest were tested (testing data) as shown in Figure 3.

k-Fold Cross-Validation

Fig. 3. Cross-Validation Methods

The second part is to optimize the model using the Confusion Matrix Performance tool. Its components consist of accuracy measurement, precision measurement, and recall measurement as detailed and calculated in Figure 4.

Confusion Matrix Performance

		Actual Class		Precision
		Positive	Negative	
Predicted Class	Positive	True Positive : TP	False Positive: FP (Type 1 Error)	Positive Predictive Value : $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
	Negative	False Negative : FN (Type 2 Error)	True Negative: TN	Negative Predictive Value : $\frac{TN}{TN+FN}$
Recall		Sensitivity : $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$	Specificity : $\frac{TN}{TN+FP}$	
Accuracy :		$\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$		

Fig. 4. Confusion Matrix Performance

The final part was to test the selected models with the data collected initially to determine the accuracy of the model's prediction results. This process takes place after a suitable model is obtained.

Deployment

Deployment (D) phase is the process of applying the discovered prototype model to a research or business problem (Chapman et al., 2000; Wirth & Hipp, 2000). The aim of the implementation of this research is to develop an application based on an assessed and quality model. Applications that are expected to be adapted include mobile application, web application, application on the cloud, and so on.

Research Results

The research results are divided into four sections: data collection report, data analysis report, model development report, and model evaluation report.

Data Collection Report

The research population is students in the University of Phayao. It consists of eleven affiliations: School of Agriculture and Natural Resources, School of Business and Communication Arts, School of Education, School of Engineering, School of Information and Communication Technology, School of Law, School of Liberal Arts, School of Medical Sciences, School of Medicine, School of Political and Social Science, School of Science. The scope of data collection is during the first semester of the academic year 2020, and the second semester of the academic year 2020. It had a total of 925 students who responded to the questionnaire as detailed in Table 5, and Table 6. The data collected is stored at <https://bit.ly/3rhg7vx>. It does not disclose or trace back who provided the data.

Table 5. Data Collection Classified with Affiliation and Gender

Affiliation	Gender		Total
	Female	Male	
School of Agriculture and Natural Resources	30 (3.24%)	7 (0.76%)	37 (4.00%)

Affiliation	Gender		Total
	Female	Male	
School of Business and Communication Arts	110 (11.89%)	45 (4.86%)	155 (16.76%)
School of Education	126 (13.62%)	33 (3.57%)	159 (17.19%)
School of Engineering	38 (4.11%)	56 (6.05%)	94 (10.16%)
School of Information and Communication Technology	16 (1.73%)	55 (5.95%)	71 (7.68%)
School of Law	19 (2.05%)	14 (1.51%)	33 (3.57%)
School of Liberal Arts	39 (4.22%)	18 (1.95%)	57 (6.16%)
School of Medical Sciences	87 (9.41%)	8 (0.86%)	95 (10.27%)
School of Medicine	92 (9.95%)	14 (1.51%)	106 (11.46%)
School of Political and Social Science	29 (3.14%)	36 (3.89%)	65 (7.03%)
School of Science	34 (3.68%)	19 (2.05%)	53 (5.73%)
Total:	620 (67.03%)	305 (32.97%)	925 (100.00%)

Table 5 shows the data collection classified by affiliation and gender. It found that the majority of respondents were female (620 students: 67.03%) rather than male (305 students: 32.97%). In addition, it also found that the affiliation with the highest number of respondents was the School of Education, which consisted of 159 students (17.19%). While the smallest respondent was the School of Agriculture and Natural Resources, which consisted of 37 students (4.00%).

Table 6. Data Collection Classified with Affiliation and Year

Affiliation	Year				
	1	2	3	4	5
School of Agriculture and Natural Resources	9 (0.97%)	11 (1.19%)	6 (0.65%)	10 (1.08%)	1 (0.11%)
School of Business and Communication Arts	75 (8.11%)	37 (4.00%)	23 (2.49%)	18 (1.95%)	2 (0.22%)
School of Education	67 (7.24%)	21 (2.27%)	30 (3.24%)	38 (4.11%)	3 (0.32%)
School of Engineering	34 (3.68%)	20 (2.16%)	24 (2.59%)	7 (0.76%)	9 (0.97%)
School of Information and Communication Technology	23 (2.49%)	22 (2.38%)	12 (1.30%)	14 (1.51%)	0 (0.00%)
School of Law	10 (1.08%)	5 (0.54%)	8 (0.86%)	9 (0.97%)	1 (0.11%)
School of Liberal Arts	15 (1.62%)	11 (1.19%)	20 (2.16%)	10 (1.08%)	1 (0.11%)
School of Medical Sciences	37 (4.00%)	27 (2.92%)	19 (2.05%)	11 (1.19%)	1 (0.11%)
School of Medicine	28 (3.03%)	19 (2.05%)	22 (2.38%)	35 (3.78%)	2 (0.22%)
School of Political and Social Science	11 (1.19%)	18 (1.95%)	20 (2.16%)	15 (1.62%)	1 (0.11%)
School of Science	20 (2.16%)	12 (1.30%)	10 (1.08%)	11 (1.19%)	0 (0.00%)
Total:	329 (35.57%)	203 (21.95%)	194 (20.97%)	178 (19.24%)	21 (2.27%)

Table 6 shows the data collection classified by affiliation and year. It was found that the most of respondents were studied in the first year, which consisted of 329 students (35.57%). The second was studied in the second year, which consisted of 203 students (21.95%). The third was studied in the third year, which consisted of 194 students (20.97%). The last was studied in the fifth year, which consisted of 21 students (2.27%). Table 5 and Table 6 present the data collected and present a fundamental analysis to enumerate the frequency and origin of the data. The next section is the analysis and interpretation of the data with the basic statistical tools, and interpretation of DASS-21.

Data Analysis Report

This report section consists of two parts: The first part is an analysis of attitudes and perceptions in the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic. The second part is an analysis of the risks for depression, anxiety, and stress. The results of the 2 analyzes are shown in Table 7, and Table 8.

Table 7. Scenario Analysis of Coronavirus Disease (Covid-19) Impact

Perspective	Scenario Analysis		
	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
Learning Management Dimensions			
1. Problems of opening/closing the semester	2.96	0.90	Large Impact
2. Online learning methods	3.33	0.80	Most Severe Impact
3. Equipment in online learning	2.96	0.93	Large Impact
4. How to access the online learning system	2.94	0.82	Large Impact
5. Impact on learning	2.38	0.77	Moderate Impact
Economic, Social, and Daily Life Dimensions			
6. Impact of university travel	2.67	0.91	Large Impact
7. Services and welfare in the university	2.68	0.92	Large Impact
8. Impact of university activities	3.07	0.96	Large Impact
9. University lifestyle	2.89	0.85	Large Impact
10. Impact of the government measures	3.06	0.82	Large Impact

Interpersonal Dimension			
11. Impact of relationships between friends	2.24	1.08	Moderate Impact
12. Impact of family relationships	1.98	1.05	Moderate Impact
Average:	2.85	0.99	Large Impact

Table 7 summarizes attitudes and perceptions on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic situation. It consists of three dimensions and twelve questions. The overall analysis revealed that the majority of respondents were large affected. Whereas the biggest concern the respondents raised was the online learning methods. It had the highest level of impact with an average of 3.33 (S.D. = 0.80). However, respondents pointed that family relationships are not affected by the COVID-19 situation. It had the lowest level of impact with an average of 1.98 (S.D. = 1.05).

Table 8. DASS-21 Analysis

Level	DASS-21 Analysis		
	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
Normal	712 (76.97%)	745 (80.54%)	857 (92.65%)
Mild	137 (14.81%)	70 (7.57%)	57 (6.16%)
Moderate	73 (7.89%)	94 (10.16%)	11 (1.19%)
Severe	3 (0.32%)	15 (1.62%)	0 (0.00%)
Extremely Severe	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)

Table 8 presents an analysis of the risks for depression, anxiety, and stress. Overall, it is gratifying that the majority of respondents have a normal risk level for all indications. However, some respondents were found to be at risk. It includes depression risk group, which is mostly mild level (137 students: 14.81%). The anxiety risk group, which is mostly moderate level (94 students: 10.16%). Finally, the stress risk group, which is mostly mild level (57 students: 6.16%). The data and results from Table 8 are important tools used to measure the relationship of attitudes toward the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the risk of depression, the risk of anxiety disorders, and the risk of stress. Where, the researcher used these data and results to develop a decision tree model for predicting disease risk.

Model Development Report

The components of the developed model report consist of 3 subsections. Each reported element is presented in three tables: Table 9 decision tree model for depression risk analysis, Table 10 decision tree model for anxiety risk analysis, and Table 11 decision tree model for stress risk analysis. In addition, each table uses a cross-validation method to show the accuracy of each model.

Table 9. Decision Tree Model for Depression Risk Analysis

Depth of Decision Tree	Accuracy from Cross-Validation Method (k-Fold)			
	10-Fold	50-Fold	100-Fold	Leave-one-out
5*	73.40%	72.33%	72.72%	72.76%*
6	72.11%	71.36%	72.27%	71.78%
7	72.00%	70.81%	71.53%	71.03%
8	71.78%	70.48%	71.21%	70.59%

* Highest accuracy

Table 9 shows the development of a decision tree model for depressive risk analysis based on various criteria. It was found that the model with the highest accuracy was the model with a depth of 5 with leave-one-out cross-validation has the highest accuracy of 72.76%. The performance is shown in Table 12.

Table 10. Decision Tree Model for Anxiety Risk Analysis

Depth of Decision Tree	Accuracy from Cross-Validation Method (k-Fold)			
	10-Fold	50-Fold	100-Fold	Leave-one-out
5*	78.05%	77.95%	78.37%*	78.27%
6	76.54%	76.66%	76.39%	76.43%
7	76.32%	76.34%	75.97%	76.11%
8	76.11%	75.91%	75.64%	75.78%

* Highest accuracy

Table 10 shows the development of a decision tree model for anxiety risk analysis based on various criteria. It was found that the model with the highest accuracy was the model with a depth of 5 with 100-Fold cross-validation has the highest accuracy of 78.37%. The performance test details are shown in Table 13.

Table 11. Decision Tree Model for Stress Risk Analysis

Depth of Decision Tree	Accuracy from Cross-Validation Method (k-Fold)			
	10-Fold	50-Fold	100-Fold	Leave-one-out
5*	91.35%	91.78%	91.80%	91.78%*
6	90.59%	91.35%	91.27%	91.35%
7	90.38%	91.13%	90.82%	91.03%
8	90.38%	91.02%	90.82%	91.03%

* Highest accuracy

Table 11 shows the development of a decision tree model for stress risk analysis based on various criteria. It was found that the model with the highest accuracy was the model with a depth of 5 with leave-one-out cross-validation has the highest accuracy of 91.78%. The performance is shown in Table 14.

Model Evaluation Report

The model performance report sections refer to the models considered in the previous section as detailed in Tables 12 to Table 14.

Table 12. Decision Tree Model Performance for Depression Risk Analysis

Accuracy: 72.76%	True Actual				Class Precision
	Normal	Moderate	Mild	Severe	
Pred. Normal	658	62	126	3	77.50%
Pred. Moderate	27	9	5	0	21.95%
Pred. Mild	27	2	6	0	17.14%
Pred. Severe	0	0	0	0	0.00%
Class Recall	92.42%	12.33%	4.38%	0.00%	

Table 12 shows the performance of the model selected from the decision tree model for depression risk analysis as shown in Table 9. It found that the accuracy of the model was high (72.76%). However, when considering the sub-indicators, it was found that some classes have very low accuracy values, for example, the moderate class predictions were found to have only 4.38% accuracy compared to the normal class as high accuracy as 92.42%.

Table 13. Decision Tree Model Performance for Anxiety Risk Analysis

Accuracy: 78.37%	True Actual					Class Precision
	Normal	Moderate	Mild	Severe	Extremely Severe	
Pred. Normal	720	88	65	14	1	81.08%
Pred. Moderate	17	5	5	1	0	17.86%
Pred. Mild	6	1	0	0	0	0.00%
Pred. Severe	2	0	0	0	0	0.00%
Pred. Extremely Severe	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%
Class Recall	96.64%	5.32%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	

Table 13 shows the performance of the model selected from the decision tree model for anxiety risk analysis as shown in Table 10. It found that the accuracy of the model was high (78.37%). It is in the same direction as the previous table. Sub-indicators were found that some classes have very low accuracy values, for example, the moderate class predictions were found to have only 5.32% accuracy compared to the normal class as high accuracy as 92.42%.

Table 14. Decision Tree Model Performance for Stress Risk Analysis

Accuracy: 91.78%	True Actual			Class Precision
	Normal	Mild	Moderate	
Pred. Normal	849	56	9	92.89%
Pred. Mild	8	0	2	0.00%
Pred. Moderate	0	1	0	0.00%
Class Recall	99.07%	0.00%	0.00%	

Table 14 shows the performance of the model selected from the decision tree model for stress risk analysis as shown in Table 11. It found that the accuracy of the model was very high (91.78%). While the problem arises is that in sub-answer classes it is not possible to predict other answer classes.

Research Discussion

In the research discussion, the researcher wants to clearly discuss the issues that affect the research objectives. The major goal of this research is to develop a model to predict the relationship between the impact arising from the COVID-19 pandemic on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress.

The results of studies and research to develop the model found that there were obstacles to the model's performance. Although all the selected models had a high level of accuracy, some indicators of sub-class had the lowest accuracy.

For example, Table 14 shows a very high accuracy of the decision tree model performance for stress risk analysis with an accuracy of 91.78%. On the contrary, other sub-classes cannot be predicted at all. Another example is Table 13 that shows the same problem. It has been found that some sub-classes have very high accuracy values (the normal class had 96.64% accuracy), while some sub-classes have very low accuracy values (the moderate class had 5.32% accuracy, the mild class had 0.00% accuracy, the severe class had 0.00% accuracy, and the extremely severe class had 0.00% accuracy). It reflects the need to select specific attributes to improve model performance in subcomponents. A viable solution is to implement a feature selection method in the prediction model. It is an important solution for solving future problems.

Another issue that the researchers expected to affect the model's performance was the number of samples most of whom were not at risk for depression, anxiety, and stress. It can be clearly seen from Table 8 that there are more data of normal samples than abnormal samples. One problem with developing a good model is having the right and close proportion of the data. This problem was solved by clustering. Therefore, an important solution to this problem is to cluster appropriately for analysis, with the researcher planning further research to address this issue. The research process that will solve the problem in the future is to optimize the sample by designing the appropriate group and solving the problem of model performance that is either too high or too low accuracy.

Conclusion

The important findings of this research reveal that the influence of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic does not aggravate the mental health of students at the University of Phayao. From the objectives of this research to be determined that (1) to investigate the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education, (2) to formulate a reasonable predictive model of the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education with machine learning, and (3) to evaluate a predictive model of the relationship between the impact of the Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic scenario on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress of students in higher education.

Conclusions can be summarized as follows: (1) the relationship of the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic situation on the risk of depression, anxiety, and stress is unrelated. Table 7 and Table 8 support this conclusion. Table 7 shows the overall average that the majority of respondents were affected at a large impact (average = 2.85, S.D. 0.99). While Table 8 shows that most of the respondents were at normal risk level in all indicators (depression at normal risk = 712 respondents: 76.97%, anxiety at normal risk = 745 respondents: 80.54%, and stress at normal risk = 857 respondents: 92.65%). It seems to be opposite each other. (2) Models developed for predicting depression, anxiety and stress risk were highly accurate across all models.

However, when analyzed the model's performance, it was found that some sub-classes were ineffective in the predictions, as mentioned in the results discussion section. Therefore, further research is a great needed to address the problem of not being able to comprehensively predict subclasses. Finally, the findings in this research provide inspiration and development efforts to further develop the body of knowledge and address global problems.

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